

EFFECT OF PASTING AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF FLOURS AND STARCHES FROM ONE INDIGENOUS AND THREE IMPROVED LOCAL WHITE RICE

Mustapha, H.M^{1*}, Dandago, M.A², Dawi, A.W³, Danbaba N¹, Sogunle, K.A¹, Ismail A.R¹ and Ogbu, L.U³

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Abstract

This study evaluated the pasting and thermal properties of flours and starches produced from four different rice varieties, including one indigenous and three improved local white rice varieties (Faro 44, 52, 61, and kwandala). The four samples (local rice varieties) were purchased from the National Rice Research Institute Badeggi, Niger, and were further processed into flours and starches. Thermal and pasting properties of the flours and starches were determined. The results obtained for the thermal properties of the rice starch showed that the onset gelatinization of the rice starches T_o ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) ranged from 63.45°C to 78.31°C , the peak of gelatinization T_p was 66.77°C to 80.01°C , and the gelatinization conclusion T_c ranged from 72.01°C to 86.29°C . The gelatinization enthalpy, ΔH_G ranged from 1.30°C to 2.48°C . J/g and the melting range ($T_c - T_o$) $5.42 - 15.08^{\circ}\text{C}$ in all four samples. The results of the pasting properties of the improved rice flours showed that the peak viscosity (PV cp) ranged from 2241.33 to 3312.45 and the trough viscosity (TV cp) ranged from 2007.67 to 2903.07. Breakdown (BD cp) 233.66 – 834.38, Final viscosity (FV cp): 4805.00–5678.00; setback (SBV cp): 2155.00–3142.41; peak time (PT): 5.96–6.11; and pasting temperature (Peak temp): 79.94–82.13. The results of the pasting properties of rice starch showed that the peak viscosity (PV cp) ranged from 4869.67 to 5439.33 and the trough viscosity (TV cp) ranged from 2328.67 to 3902.38. Breakdown (BDV cp) 1536.95 - 3014, Final viscosity (FV cp) 4356.00 - 6426.00, setback (SBV cp) 3089.33 - 3413.33, peak time PT (min) 4.28 - 5.27 and the pasting temperature (Peak temp): 62.02–70.37. The properties of flours and starches from the indigenous and improved Nigerian rice cultivars should have desirable quality properties relevant for the postharvest value addition chain.

¹Department of Food Science and Technology, Faculty of Renewable Natural Resources, Federal University Dutsin-ma Katsina, Nigeria

²Department of Food Science and Technology, Aliko Dangote University of Science and Technology, Wudil, PMB 3013, Kano State, Nigeria

³Department of Food Science and Technology, Federal University of Agriculture Mubi, P.M.B 2025 Adamawa State, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Rice has been processed and used in the production of numerous products for centuries. However, local rice varieties show superior nutritional quality, particularly in terms of the amounts of minerals, such as potassium, calcium, and protein (Diako *et al.*, 2010). *Oryza glaberrima* is a domesticated wild forebear found along the Niger River in Mali, West Africa, over 3,500 years ago (Alaka and Okafar, 2018). *Oryza sativa* is more diversified than *Oryza glaberrima* because it is present worldwide but is particularly concentrated on Asia. The sticky, short-grained Japonica varieties and the non-sticky, long-grained *Indica* variety are the two most widely cultivated subspecies of *Oryza sativa*.

Two common rice varieties have been observed: the photosensitive variety that thrives in deep water and the early erect variety that thrives in both lowland and upland ecosystems (Asaoka *et al.*, 2015). African rice has certain advantageous traits, such as its ability to compete with weeds for nutrients (Jones *et al.*, 2017), drought resistance, acidity, and iron toxicity (Almeida *et al.*, 2017), and ability to adapt to low input circumstances (Sarla and Swanmy, 2017). Furthermore, according to Basorun (2013), African rice is nematodes-resistant, stem borer, and rice yellow mottle virus.

One of the key benefits of African rice over Asian rice is its tolerance to many biotic pressures, including diseases, insects, and nematodes, as well as abiotic challenges, including drought, flooding, and salinity. It still has a low yield and a high tendency to shatter, resulting in significant post-harvest losses. Because rice breaks quickly, conventional milling also produces significant number of broken rice (Sarla and Swamy, 2017; Bao *et al.*, 2019). Owing to its adaptability, ceremonial significance, and cultural relevance, some African farmers continue to grow African rice despite these obstacles.

The majority of consumers prefer long rice (medium and high amylose) because of its ability to hold together after preparation. When making sticky foods, such as *Tuwon shinkafa*, which must be molded into solid shapes, sticky (high amylopectin) local white rice varieties are employed (Nkama, 2017). These variants include some that are regarded as "traditional" types. In the past 20 years, new ones have been introduced. New varieties are generated and distributed by research institutes or imports from Asia (Danbaba *et al.*, 2012). A political figure brought local white rice, known as "China," to Nigeria about 20 years ago, and it has since spread throughout the country despite the unsatisfactory seed trials of the National Cereal Research Institute (NCRI) (Maji, 2010; Biswa and Juliano, 2017). There is a need to increase the competitiveness of local white rice, particularly considering its nutritious makeup (Maji, 2010). Owing to its high starch content, rice increases the sugar level in the body, and excess glucose in the blood is turned into fat. Thus, the excess consumption of rice flour can lead to weight gain and the development of overweight and obesity. Hence, this study focused on the evaluation of the pasting and thermal properties of flour and starch from one indigenous and three improved varieties of local white rice.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sources of raw materials

Four varieties of improved Paddy rice (Faro 44, 52, and 61) and the indigenously local Kwandala variety (*Badankama*) were procured from the National Cereal Research Institute, Badeggi, Niger State, and Kano Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (KNARDA).

The tools and equipment used in this study were obtained from the Food Processing Laboratory, Kano State University of Science and Technology, Wudil. The samples were processed in the food processing laboratory of the Department of Food Science and Technology, Wudil, Kano State University of Science and Technology. All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade.

Production of local white rice flour

Figure 1: Diagram for rice flour production

Source: Adopted and modified methods of Conde *et al.* (2019) and Adebowale *et al.* (2018).

Extraction of rice starch

Rice starch was extracted from processed paddy rice flour using an alkali extraction method following a method described by Lawal *et al.* (2011). One kilogram (1 kg) of rice flour was mixed with 1 L of 0.2 % NaOH solution. The mixture was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 20 min and allowed to stand for 24h at 25°C for 24 h to soften the endosperm. The supernatant was decanted, and a fresh volume of sodium hydroxide (0.2 % NaOH) was added to the solid phase and stirred at ambient temperature for another 3 h. The procedure was repeated twice, after which the solid phase was washed with 0.2 % NaOH. The procedure was repeated several times until the supernatant became clear and neutralized to the biuret test for proteins (Cardoso *et al.*, 2017). All particles that formed yellow tailings were removed from the starch residue surface. The starch was suspended in two-fold volumes of distilled water and centrifuged for 10 min. The washed starch was re-slurred with distilled water and centrifuged again. The isolated starch residue was collected and dried in an oven at 40 °C for 48 h. The dried starch was pulverized into a smooth flouring powder using a friction-type laboratory milling machine (Yanmar HS 1000 EH, Japan). The isolated starch was passed through a 100-µm mesh sieve and stored in a zip-lock bag for further analysis. The flow diagram for rice starch production is shown in Fig 1.

ANALYTICAL METHODS

Thermal Properties

The thermal properties of rice starch were analyzed using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC-204, Netzsch, Germany) according to the method described by Cardoso *et al.* (2017). Rice starch samples (dry basis, 40 mg) were pressed and placed in aluminum sample pans. Gelatinization was determined by heating the starch in an aluminum pan from 4°C to 450°C at a rate of C/min. The onset (T_o), peak temperatures (T_p), and enthalpy of gelatinization (ΔH) were determined, and the conclusion of gelatinization (T_c) was determined. The gelatinization range (R) was computed as ($T_c - T_o$). Enthalpies were calculated on a dry weight basis (Vasanthan 2016). The peak height index (PHI) was calculated using the ratio ($H_{gel}/T_p - T_o$). The gelatinization (melting) range (R) was calculated as follows: $MR = (T_c - T_o)$

Evaluation of the Pasting Properties

A rapid viscos-analyzer (RVA super 4, Newport Scientific Pty. Ltd., Narrabeen, Australia) was used to determine the pasting properties using the method described by Waramboi *et al.* (2011). A mixture of 3 g of flour and starch samples and distilled water was stirred in the sample canister at 960 rpm for 10 s to prevent sedimentation and then at 160 rpm for the remainder of the test. The temperature profile was started from 50°C for 1 min, followed by linearly raising the temperature linearly to 95°C in 3 min 42 s, holding for 2 min 30 s, then cooling the system to 50°C in 3 min 48 s, and ending the process in about 13 min. The viscosity breakdown ratio was defined as the ratio of the trough to the peak viscosity. A programed heating and cooling cycle. The following parameters were recorded: pasting temperature (PT), peak viscosity (PV), minimum viscosity (MV), trough viscosity (TV), final viscosity (FV), and peak time (PTime). BV was calculated as the difference between PV and MV, whereas TSV was determined as the difference between FV and MV. All determinations were performed in triplicate. ($BD = PV - MV$); set back ($SB = CPV - PV$) and consistency ($CS = CPV - HPV$). *Breakdown viscosity = PV - MV*; *Consistency = CPV - HPV*.

Statistical Analysis

All data were obtained in three replicates, and the results were reported as an average value (mean \pm standard deviation). Data were analyzed using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) model using SPSS Version 2010. Fisher's Least Significant Difference was used for multiple mean comparison tests. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal properties of rice starches

Table 1 presents the thermal properties of the isolated rice starch samples using the DSC. The transition temperatures (onset of gelatinization temperature, peak of gelatinization temperature, and conclusion of gelatinization temperature) and gelatinization temperature range increased with temperature. The transition temperatures (T_o , T_p , and T_c) and enthalpy of gelatinization (ΔH_{gel}) from various rice cultivars differed significantly ($p < 0.05$). The onset of gelatinization temperature (T_o) of the isolated rice starch samples from *Kwandala*, Faro 44, Faro 52, and Faro 61 ranged from 75.85°C to 78.31 °C, with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among all the samples. The peak of gelatinization temperature (T_p) of the isolated rice starch from samples coded *Kwandala*, Faro 44, Faro 52, and Faro 61 ranged from 78.99 - 80.01 °C without a significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between Faro 61 *kwandala*, while Faro 44 and Faro 52 were significant at ($p > 0.05$).

The gelatinization temperature (T_c) of the isolated rice starch samples in samples coded *Kwandala*, Faro 44, Faro 52, and Faro 61 ranged from 72.01°C to 86.29 °C, followed by the enthalpy of gelatinization ΔH_g (H_g) which ranged from 1.30°C to 2.48°C. J/g, with a significant difference at ($p < 0.05$) among all the samples. Similarly, the

melting point ($T_c - T_o$) of the isolated rice starch samples ranged from 5.42 °C to 15.06 °C, with significant differences among the samples at ($p < 0.05$). There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between Faro 52 and Faro 61.

Table 1: Thermal properties of rice starches

Samples	T_o (°C)	T_p (°C)	T_c (°C)	ΔHG (J/g)	MR ($T_c - T_o$)
<i>Kwandala</i>	75.85 ^b ±0.01	78.99 ^a ±0.01	86.29 ^a ±1.36	2.07 ^b ±0.04	10.43 ^b ±1.36
Faro 44	63.45 ^d ±0.03	68.51 ^b ±0.81	78.51 ^b ±0.74	2.48 ^a ±0.01	15.06 ^a ±0.74
Faro 52	63.71 ^c ±0.02	66.77 ^b ±3.34	72.01 ^c ±1.80	1.55 ^c ±0.02	8.31 ^{bc} ±1.79
Faro 61	78.31 ^a ±0.08	80.01 ^a ±0.03	83.72 ^a ±2.49	1.30 ^d ±0.01	5.42 ^c ±2.54
LSD	0.26	3.24	3.24	0.06	3.27

Values are means ± Standard deviation of three replicates. Means with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Key: T_o , onset gelatinization temperature; T_p , peak gelatinization temperature; T_c -Conclusion gelatinization Temperature; ΔH - Enthalpy of gelatinization; MR, melting range ($T_c - T_o$).

Pasting properties of rice flours

The pasting properties of rice starch are presented in Table 2. Where the peak viscosity of the local rice starch coded (*Kwandala*) and three improved varieties (Faro 44, Faro 52, and Faro 61) ranged from 2241.33 to 3737.45, there was a significantly difference at ($p < 0.05$) among all the samples. The results of trough viscosity obtained from the four selected samples ranged from 2007.67 to 2903.07 cP, followed by the breakdown viscosity of the rice flours, which ranged from 233.66 to 834.38 cP with a noticeable difference at ($p < 0.05$) among all the samples. Sample Faro 52 (233.66 cP) had the lowest mean value, whereas sample Faro 44 (834.38 cP) had the highest mean breakdown viscosity value. The results of the final viscosity of the rice flours ranged from the lowest to the highest in sample *Kwandala*–Faro 44 (4805.00 - 5678.00 cP). There was a significant difference at ($p < 0.05$) among all the samples analyzed. The setback viscosity of the four selected rice flour samples ranged from 2155.00 to 3142.410 cP. Meanwhile, the peak time of the rice flour samples ranged from 5.96°C to 6.11°C, and the pasting temperature of the rice flour ranged from 79.94°C to 80.38 °C. There was a significant difference among the samples at ($p < 0.05$) between *Kwandala* and Faro 44, 52, and 51

Table 2: Pasting properties of improved rice flours

Sample	PV cP	TV Cp	BDV cP	FV cP	SBV cP	PT(min)	PTemp
<i>Kwandala</i>	3312.45 ^b ±12.53	2879.36 ^b ±0.57	433.09 ^c ±2.08	4805.00 ^d ±49.49	2426.67 ^c ±7.09	6.06 ^a ±0.01	80.38 ^b ±0.63
Faro 44	3737.45 ^a ±32.98	2903.07 ^a ±3.03	834.38 ^a ±2.31	5678.00 ^a ±7.55	3142.41 ^a ±5.89	6.11 ^a ±0.02	80.07 ^b ±0.08
Faro 52	2241.33 ^d ±1.15	2007.67 ^c ±5.86	233.66 ^d ±1.51	4947.33 ^c ±4.62	2155.00 ^d ±45.92	5.97 ^b ±0.02	82.13 ^a ±0.12
Faro 61	2802.85 ^c ±10.93	2013.00 ^c ±2.00	789.85 ^b ±0.60	5102.33 ^b ±6.51	3017.07 ^b ±5.25	5.96 ^b ±0.06	79.94 ^b ±0.01
LSD	34.81	6.517	3.305	47.76	44.41	0.06	1.705

Values are means ± Standard deviation of three replicate determinations. Means with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). PV: peak viscosity; TV: trough viscosity; BD: breakdown (PV-HPV); FV: final viscosity; SB: setback; PT: peak time; peak temp: pasting temperature.

Pasting Properties of Isolated Rice Starches

The results of the pasting properties of isolated starches analyzed by the Rapid Visco-Analyzer are presented in Table 3, where the peak viscosity ranged from 4869.67 to 5439.33 cP. The trough viscosity (minimum viscosity) of the extracted rice starches ranged from 3118.68 to 3902.38 and 2328.67 to 3902.38 cP. Sample coded Faro 61 had the lowest mean value, while sample coded Faro 44 had the highest. The results of the breakdown viscosities of the isolated rice starches ranged from 3014, 1833.65 to 1805.33 cP in sample coded faro 52 to *kwandala*,

1536.95 to 3014.00 cP, with an observable significant difference at ($p < 0.05$) among all the samples analyzed. The final viscosity ranged from 4356.00 to 6426.00 cp. Sample coded Faro 61 had the lowest mean value, while sample coded Faro 4 had the highest. The setback viscosity of the rice starches extracted showed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) among all the samples analyzed, ranging from 3089.33 to 3413.33 cp. The peak time of the extracted rice starches ranged from 4.28 to 5.27 in samples coded Faro 52 and was the highest in Faro 44. The pasting temperature of the extracted rice starches revealed a significant difference among the samples in samples coded Faro 61 to kwandala with a mean value of 62.02 – 70.37 at ($p < 0.05$) while there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between samples coded Faro 52 (62.53°C) and Faro 61 (62.02°C).

Table 3: Pasting properties of rice starches

Samples	PV cP	TV Cp	BDV cP	FV cP	SBV cP	PT(min)	PTemp(°C)
Kwandala	4952.33 ^c ±63.58	3118.68 ^b ±16.66	1833.65 ^a ±4.45	4953.67 ^c ±47.35	3305.33 ^b ±3.21	5.27 ^d ±0.03	70.37 ^c ±0.59
Faro 44	5439.33 ^a ±35.10	3902.38 ^a ±2.12	1805.33 ^c ±4.74	6426.00 ^a ±32.60	3296.67 ^c ±3.21	5.05 ^c ±0.02	60.66 ^a ±0.02
Faro 52	4869.67 ^c ±1.53	3103.34 ^b ±8.39	1536.95 ^b ±4.02	5152.67 ^b ±30.06	3089.33 ^{sd} ±2.08	4.28 ^a ±0.02	62.53 ^b ±0.08
Faro 61	5342.67 ^b ±49.50	2328.67 ^c ±12.62	3014.00 ^a ±24.73	4356.00 ^d ±32.28	3413.33 ^a ±1.53	4.39 ^b ±0.05	62.02 ^b ±0.07
LSD	82.83	123.40	3.305	47.76	0.05	0.06	0.57

Values are means ±Standard deviation of three replicate determinations. Means with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).PV: peak viscosity; TV: trough viscosity; BD: breakdown (PV-HPV); FV: final viscosity; SB: setback; PT: peak time; peak temp: pasting temperature.

DISCUSSION

Thermal properties of the rice starches

The transition temperatures (onset of gelatinization temperature, peak of gelatinization temperature, and conclusion of gelatinization temperature) and gelatinization temperature range increased with increasing temperature. The transition temperatures (T_o , T_p , and T_c) and enthalpy of gelatinization (ΔH_{gel}) from various rice cultivars differed significantly ($p < 0.05$). The onset of the gelatinization temperature (T_o) of the isolated rice starch samples ranged between 63.45°C and 78.31°C. The values were similar to those reported by Bao *et al.* (2019), who reported values of 65.02°C and 68.41°C for the functional properties of indigenous Nigerian rice varieties, but higher than those reported by Alaka and Koakak (2018), who reported values of 50.8°C and 68.8°C for six varieties of Nigerian rice cultivars. The onset temperature (T_o) determine the boundaries of the different phases in a semi-crystalline material such as starch (Biliaderis *et al.*, 2019). Faro 61 having the highest onset of gelatinization temperature (T_o) may be due to higher amylose content, and sample (B) with the lowest onset of gelatinization temperature may be due to its low amylose content.

The results of the peak of gelatinization temperature (T_p) were consistent with the findings of Lawal *et al.* (2011), who reported T_p in this study 81.5 and 88.5°C for starches isolated from West African rice cultivars, but were lower than the results obtained by Falade *et al.* (2014). A high degree of crystallinity provides structural stability and makes the granule more resistant to gelatinization, which accounts for the high transition temperatures (T_o , T_c , and T_p) (Barichello *et al.*, 2019). The enthalpy of gelatinization ΔH_g (H_g) of the isolated rice starch samples ranged between {1.30-2.48J/g. The values were lower than the values obtained by Bondeson *et al.* (2019), which varied between 7.58 and 17.35 J/g for six Nigerian rice cultivars. The difference in the enthalpy of gelatinization (ΔH_g) indicate rupturing of links between and within the amylopectin double helices (Cooke and Gidley 2016). Double helical and crystalline structures are disrupted in starches during gelatinization. The high enthalpy of gelatinization (ΔH_g) of the Faro 44 sample indicates a more stable structure that is relatively more resistant to granule swelling to preserve granule integrity and exhibit shear stability. This resulted in a negligible breakdown (Gryszkin *et al.*, 2019).

Pasting properties of rice flours

The peak viscosity (Table 2) had a similar value to that obtained by Falade *et al.* (2014), which ranged from 2376.0 to 3988.5 cP for the six Nigerian rice flours. At a constant shear rate, the starch sample of *Kwandala* and Faro 44 demonstrates greater resistance to shear stress and can carry a higher viscous load than that encountered during mixing operations. High peak viscosity is significant in the preparation of stiff dough products (Thomas and Atwell *et al.*, 2019). Peak viscosity indicates water-binding capacity and is often correlated with the quality of the final product (Thomas and Atwell, 2019). The trough viscosity (minimum viscosity) is the point at which the viscosity reaches its minimum during either the heating or cooling process. Peak viscosity is usually followed by a breakdown to minimum (trough viscosity) as a result of starch granules rupture and leach during exposure to high temperature and shear (Bondeson *et al.*, 2015). Trough viscosity (minimum viscosity) measures the ability of the pastes to withstand breakdown during cooling. The significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) high trough viscosity indicated the tendency of Faro 44 rice flour to break down during cooking (Ashogbon and Akintayo, 2012a).

The breakdown viscosity is a measure of the ease with which swollen granules can disintegrate (Lawal *et al.*, 2017). For rice, a higher breakdown is considered an indicator of better palatability. Adebowale *et al.* (2005) reported that the higher the breakdown viscosity, the lower the ability of the rice flour to withstand heating and shear stress during cooking. These findings were in accordance with the findings of Bondeson *et al.* (2015), who reported similar results, showing that the *Kwandala* sample had the lowest final viscosity and the Faro 44 sample had the highest final viscosity. The final viscosity is the most commonly used parameter to determine the quality of a particular starch-based sample. This gives an idea of the starch ability to gel after cooking. The gelatinization temperature (GT) indicates the temperature range in which at least 90% of starch granules swell irreversibly in hot water with loss of crystallinity and birefringence (Cruz *et al.*, 2020).

Peak time is a measure of cooking time. The minimum temperature required to heat the flour. This indicates that the Faro 61 sample, which has the lowest peak time of the improved rice flours, requires a minimum temperature during cooking compared with the other samples (Falade *et al.*, 2014).

The pasting temperature of the improved rice flours ranged from 79.94°C to 82.13 °C. The values were similar to those reported by Falade *et al.* (2014), which ranged from 82.35 to 86.40 h/°C for the six Nigerian rice varieties, but higher than those reported by Chinma *et al.* (2018), who reported values of 50.45°C and 62.54°C for five varieties of Nigerian rice flours. However, the Faro 61 sample had the lowest pasting temperature, and the Faro 52 sample had the highest pasting temperature. The pasting temperature of the rice flours under study varied significantly ($p > 0.05$). The higher pasting temperature of the Faro 52 sample implies that higher energy costs would be required during cooking (Ashogbon and Akintayo, 2012b).

Pasting Properties of the Extracted Rice Starches

Peak viscosity of the rice starches at 4869.67 and 5439.33 cP (Table 3). The values agreed with the values obtained by Falade and Okafor (2015), who reported the values of some Nigerian rice flours in the range of 4893–6080 cP. A similar range of peak viscosities of 2376.0 and 3988.5 cP was reported for six Nigerian rice flours by Falade *et al.* (2014). At a constant shear rate, the Faro 44 and Faro 61 samples would demonstrate greater resistance to shear stress and would be able to carry a higher viscous load that could be encountered during mixing operations. The trough viscosity (minimum viscosity) of the extracted rice starches ranged between 2328.67 and 3902.38 cP (Table 4.9). The values agreed with the values reported by Falade *et al.* (2014), who reported values ranging from 2176.5 to 4036.50 cP for the six Nigerian rice varieties. The significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) high trough viscosity indicated the tendency of isolated Faro 44 rice starches to break down during cooking. Differences in breakdown

viscosities among rice starches are related to differences in the rigidity of swollen granules. (Sandhya *et al.*, 2017; Karim *et al.*, 2020).

Breakdown viscosity is a measure of the cooked starch's vulnerability or susceptibility to disintegration. The higher the breakdown viscosity, the lower the ability of the starch sample to withstand heating and shear stress during cooking (Adebowale *et al.*, 2018; Ashogbon *et al.*, 2012a). Thus, Faro 61 starch might not withstand more heating and shear stress than other cultivars because of its higher breakdown values (Cruz *et al.*, 2020).

The setback viscosity of the rice starches extracted from the samples ranged between 3089.33 and 3413.33 cP. The values were similar to those reported by Bondeson *et al.* (2015), which ranged from 2279.5 to 3606.5 cP for six Nigerian rice varieties. The higher the setback, the more likely syneresis will take place, indicating a higher tendency for retrogradation. The difference in setback among different starches may be due to the amount and molecular weight of amylose leached from the granules and most of the gelatinized starch.

The peak time of the rice starches ranged between 4.28 and 5.27 min (Table 3). The values were similar to those reported by Chinma *et al.* (2018). Peak time is a measure of cooking time. The minimum temperature required to heat the starches. This indicates that the Faro 44 sample, which has the lowest peak time, requires a minimum temperature during cooking compared with the other samples.

The pasting temperature of the rice starches obtained in this study was similar to the values reported by Ashogbon and Akintayo (2012), with values in the range of 60.70°C–62.10°C for rice cultivars grown in Nigeria, but lower than the values reported by Huaisan *et al.* (2019). Pasting properties refer to when the starch is heated continuously in excess water with stirring, the granules swell irreversibly and burst as a result of the native starch structure breaking. Amylose then leaches out and the granules disintegrate to form a viscous paste (BeMiller, 2017). Starch pasting characteristics are usually determined by employing a rapid viscoanalyzer (RVA), rotational rheometers, or other viscometers capable of continuously recording changes in viscosity with temperature (BeMiller, 2017).

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that indigenous local rice could serve as a control compared with improved local rice in terms of thermal and pasting properties. However, the processing methods did not uniformly affect the cooking characteristics of the rice. The isolated starches of both the indigenous and improved local rice had restricted swelling and solubility patterns, presumably due to their granular characteristics. However, all the starch granules of the indigenous and improved local rice were small in size, spherical, and mostly polyhedral in shape. The thermal and pasting properties of these indigenous and improved local rice varieties indicate that they can be used in the food and non-food industries, such as paper and textile industries. The results showed that indigenous local rice is a nutritious staple crop containing most of the essential nutrients.

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